

Metal Complexes with Sulphur Donor Ligands-II. Preparation and Characterisation of Some Mixed Ligand Complexes Containing Bidentate Tertiary Amines and 1,1-Dithiolates

W. U. MALIK*, RAMESH BEMBI and V. K. BHARDWAJ

Department of Chemistry, University of Roorkee, Roorkee-247 672

Manuscript received 3 November 1981, revised 13 April 1982, accepted 9 March 1984

Mixed ligand complexes of Mn(II), Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II), Zn(II) and Cd(II) containing 1,1-dithiolates and 1,10-phenanthroline or 2,2'-bipyridyl have been prepared through a two step process. The composition of the complexes has been determined through radiometric, amperometric and potentiometric titrations. Infrared spectral data provide evidence of binding through the sulphur atoms, while the magnetic data are in accord with octahedral geometry of the complexes.

It is well established that sulphur is a potential donor for the transition metals¹. Amongst the large number of sulphur donor ligands, the complexes of 1,1- and 1,2-dithiolates have provided an indepth insight into the nature of metal-sulphur bonding and electron delocalisation²⁻⁴. Some of the complexes show potential biological activity⁵ and have found both technological and agricultural applications^{3,4,6,7}. In continuation of our efforts to prepare mixed ligand complexes with sulphur donor ligands, we have now prepared some complexes containing 1,1-dithiolates and 1,10-phenanthroline or 2,2'-bipyridyl. The 1,1-dithiolates were diethyldithiocarbamate (Dtc), 1,1-dithio-2,2-dicarboethoxy ethylene dithiolate (DED), and 1,1-dithio-2,2-diacetyl ethylene dithiolate (DMD)⁸.

Experimental

The complexes were prepared essentially by the two step method described earlier for the xanthate complexes⁹ using reagent grade chemicals. In the first step, $[M(LN_2)(H_2O)_4]^{2+}$ complexes (where LN_2 is 1,10-phenanthroline or 2,2'-bipyridyl) were prepared¹⁰. In the second step, a solution of the complex in water (1 m mol, 10 cm³) was reacted with an aqueous solution of sodium diethyl dithiocarbamate (2 m mol, 20 cm³) or DED or DMD (1 m mol in a minimum amount). The complex got precipitated on standing for 10 to 30 min.

The composition of the complexes was determined by radiometric, amperometric and potentiometric titrations⁹. Amperometric titrations were carried out on a Toshniwal manual polarograph, type CLO-2A, in conjunction with a Pye Scalamp galvanometer. The capillary characteristic was 1.77 mg^{2/3} s^{-1/2}. Potentiometric titrations were carried

out on a Toshniwal portable potentiometer using a silver-silver sulphide electrode⁹. Radiometric titrations were carried out by γ -ray scintillation spectrometer employing a NaI(Tl) crystal or a Geiger Muller counter for the β -emitter ^{115m}Cd. The isotopes were ⁵⁸Co, ⁶⁵Zn, ⁵⁴Mn and ^{115m}Cd, obtained from Bhabha Atomic Research Establishment, Trombay, as their chlorides in HCl solution.

The chemical analysis of the complexes for metal content was carried out after decomposing with conc HNO₃. Manganese, nickel and copper were estimated spectrophotometrically¹¹ while zinc, cadmium and cobalt were estimated gravimetrically¹¹. Sulphur was estimated as barium sulphate while carbon and nitrogen were estimated by standard micro-analytical methods.

The infrared spectra were recorded in KBr pellets in 4000-600 cm⁻¹ range and as Nujol mulls on polyethylene plate in 600-240 cm⁻¹ range on a Beckmann IR-20 spectrophotometer.

Results and Discussion

Preliminary studies show that Dtc substitutes the four water molecules of $[M(LN_2)(H_2O)_4]^{2+}$ to give $[M(LN_2)(Dtc)_2]$ while DED and DMD replace only two water molecules to give $[M(LN_2)(DED)(H_2O)_2]$ and $[M(LN_2)(DMD)(H_2O)_2]$, respectively. The substitution of only two water molecules by DED and DMD is expected since they are both divalent and as such can give neutral stable complexes after 1 : 1 interaction.

Radiometric titrations, both direct and reverse show single inflection points corresponding to the substitution of four water molecules for Dtc and two molecules for DED and DMD. Only one inflection, similar to our earlier work⁹, is observed

*Present address : Kashmir University, Srinagar, J & K.

in each case showing formation of only one complex and simultaneous substitution of all the water molecules.

These results are further supported in the case of Dtc complexes by potentiometric and amperometric titrations. These titrations show only single inflection points. The inflection points observed potentiometrically were much sharper compared to bidentate *tert*-amines and ethyl xanthate studied earlier⁹. Potentiometric titrations show stoichiometric complex of 1 : 2 type. Amperometric titrations, both direct and reverse, clearly envisage the complex formation with Dtc and the data are identical with our earlier work⁹. Both potentiometric and amperometric titrations were unsuccessful in the case of DED and DMD.

The results of chemical analysis are in accord with the above results.

The infrared spectral data show coordination of 1,10-phenanthroline or 2,2'-bipyridyl to the metal through nitrogen and that of the dithiolates through sulphur. The (M-N) band¹²⁻¹⁴ appears in the region of 300 cm⁻¹. The ring stretching vibration of 1,10-phenanthroline or 2,2'-bipyridyl appear in the 1600-1400 cm⁻¹ range.

The dithiolates are bidentate and can bind through both the sulphur atoms. The infrared

spectra suggests that the form I makes an important contribution to the overall structure. The spectra of dithiocarbamate complexes show two strong bands at 1500 cm⁻¹ and 1480 cm⁻¹. The band at 1500 cm⁻¹ is too high to be assigned to C-N or C=S bond or even a methyl deformation mode which does not appear above 1480 cm⁻¹. This band can be conveniently assigned¹⁵ to the S⁻-C⁺-N⁻, corresponding to a C-N bond shortened under the influence of a polar C-S bond. The 1480 cm⁻¹ band is assigned¹⁶⁻¹⁸ to the polar C-N bond which would appear somewhere between the normal C-N (1250-1350 cm⁻¹) and a normal

C=N (1640-1690 cm⁻¹). The complexes, therefore, belong to the 'thiouiride' classification¹⁹. The complexes further show the C-N stretching bands at 2800-3000 cm⁻¹ and the M-S bond around 390 cm⁻¹.

The infrared spectra of the complexes show the presence of C=C, C-S and M-S bands around 1675 cm⁻¹; 610, 840, 1100 cm⁻¹; and 390 cm⁻¹, respectively. They also show the C-H stretching in the 2800-3000 cm⁻¹ and the C=O absorption around 1700 cm⁻¹. Evidence for coordinated water in these complexes is provided by bands around 920, 770 and 640 cm⁻¹.

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